

INTEGRATED EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY FOR IMPROVING STUDENTS' REFLECTIVE COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20824848>

Abstract: Our study examined integrated educational technology in teaching a foreign language. Modern educational technologies, which are used to develop the communicative competence of students in the process of foreign language learning, are the most promising for creating an effective educational environment that ensures cooperation of all members of the educational process.

Annotatsiya: Bizning tadqiqotimiz chet tilini o'qitishda integratsiyalashgan ta'lim texnologiyasini ko'rib chiqdi. Chet tillarini o'rganish jarayonida talabalarning kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini rivojlantirish uchun qo'llaniladigan zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari ta'lim jarayonining barcha a'zolarining hamkorligini ta'minlaydigan samarali ta'lim muhitini yaratish uchun eng istiqbolli hisoblanadi.

Key words: pedagogical, psychological and methodological, interdisciplinary, integration, foreign language, educational technologies, teaching technology training, CLIL.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik, psixologik-metodik, fanlararo integratsiya, chet tili, ta'lim texnologiyalari, o'qitish texnologiyasi, texnologik trening, CLIL.

At the present stage of development of higher education, the interest of specialists in integrated foreign language teaching is due to a variety of pedagogical, psychological and methodological factors. Firstly, the teacher's task is to determine the main educational actions and subordinate integrated actions, creating conditions under which professionally oriented knowledge is acquired along with language knowledge. Secondly, interdisciplinary connections are becoming very relevant at the present stage of development of school and vocational education, the improvement of which is moving along the path of knowledge integration, which does not at all mean the elimination of systematic courses in individual subjects. They only contribute to strengthening the practical orientation of the "foreign language" subject. Modern educational technologies, which are used to develop the communicative competence of students in the process of foreign language learning, are the most promising for creating an effective educational environment that ensures cooperation of all members of the educational process. However, it should be noted that the introduction of any one teaching technology, no matter how perfect it may be, does not yet serve as a guarantee to reveal and improve the abilities of students and the creative potential of the teacher. Currently, the concept of "pedagogical technology" has firmly entered the lexicon of pedagogical and methodological science. However, there are great differences in its understanding and use. One of the most discussed contradictions associated with the trend of technologization of the educational sphere is the fuzziness in the correlation of the concepts of "teaching methodology" and "teaching technology". As noted by O.N.Igna, "in modern scientific literature the main reason for replacement the term "teaching methodology" to "technology training" is often explained by the fact that, despite to a huge arsenal of techniques presented as new, promising and at the same time due to the ongoing search for alternative methods, high and stable results in mastering an academic subject are not always achieved and

not by all students. Often, practical work using the developed methods does not meet the requirements for the level of training of students. And in this context, it is technology that is called an alternative to teaching methods.” [3,c.257]

The integration process also uses methods of teaching subject content, adequate to methods of teaching foreign languages language [2, p. 197–202].

For example, if a teacher introduces a new concept through a new interpretation, then the same method of introducing a new concept is used to acquire its meaning in a foreign language. Consequently, in the integrated learning process, subject and foreign language knowledge are simultaneously acquired - in other words, subject knowledge is acquired in a foreign language, and from here at the same time develop relevant subject and foreign language speech skills, since the latter serve as a means of developing skills in the content being studied. In modern practice of the university system of foreign language education, the technology of integrated teaching of a foreign language and subject (CLIL) has become widespread, which is due to various pedagogical, psychological and methodological factors. This technique arose on the basis of the language immersion method and content-based instruction. Language, being the main means of communication, is used in all types of activities of the subject. The teacher’s task is to determine the main educational action and subordinate integrated actions, to model the conditions under which the latter can become the acquisition of the former (i.e., various integrated courses can become a condition for the acquisition of foreign languages).

Integrated learning contributes to the implementation of the didactic principle of systematic learning, in which the formation of new knowledge, skills and abilities is carried out based on existing experience in other activities, the content, means and methods of learning are expanded, situations vary, and opportunities for individualization appear. The inclusion of various types of activities, in particular, integrated lessons in the educational process contributes to its effectiveness, since each of them in its own way activates the student, encourages him to be independent, promotes the development of aptitudes in a certain subject area, including when mastering a foreign language, deepens and expands interest in knowledge and learning in general.

The technology of subject-language or contextual language integrated learning (CLIL) is considered one of the most promising in teaching non-native and foreign languages[10]. It is aimed at developing students’ communicative competence in a foreign language in the same educational context in which general educational knowledge and skills are formed and developed [6, p. 249–252]. As scientific publications show, CLIL technology is becoming widespread in world practice. In Uzbekistan, this technology is innovative and the feasibility of its use requires research. The abbreviation CLIL stands for Content and Language Integrated Learning - the integration of teaching a foreign language and other academic disciplines. The term was first proposed by David Marsh (David Marsh, University of Jyvaskyla, Finland) in 1994 [13; 14].

In their research, scientists note that integrated learning technology allows students to develop linguistic and communicative competencies in a foreign language in the same educational context in which they form and develop general academic knowledge and skills. Integrated teaching of a foreign language and other academic disciplines within the framework of CLIL is a didactic technology that allows students to create linguistic and communicative competencies in a foreign language in the appropriate educational context in which they form and develop meta-subject knowledge and skills. When planning lessons using this technology, the required

components, the so-called “4 Cs”, are taken into account: “content” (content), “communication” (communication), “cognition” (mental abilities), “culture” (cultural knowledge) [11].

Thus, CLIL technology, as an innovative form of teaching a foreign language and non-linguistic content, can be implemented with varying degrees of immersion in a foreign language. Its implementation requires careful analysis and selection of the content of the integrated course. The implementation of content and language integrated learning (CLIL) technology suggests that content and language learning objectives will contribute to success in the field of foreign language teaching, in particular by allowing students to immediately test newly acquired language skills in the classroom, which will strengthen their self-confidence for further study.

From a methodological point of view, there is a fundamental difference between teaching a language and teaching non-linguistic disciplines in a foreign language. Language learning mainly focuses on the practice of four skills (reading, listening, speaking and writing). In teaching a non-language subject, these four skills are a means of acquiring new information and demonstrating understanding. It is this ability - to act in a foreign language in various situations - that can be considered the greatest advantage of CLIL, especially for the future profession of students who do not learn language skills that they can use later, but knowledge that they apply immediately.

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